

Electrometric Studies on the Composition of Chromium (II) Cyanomolybdate (IV)

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Tetrapotassium molybdenum octacyanide usually reacts with metal ions to give insoluble compounds¹, but in a few cases soluble compounds are also formed, such as with Cr(III)², Fe(III)³ and U(VI)⁴ ions. On reviewing the literature it has been found that no attempt has yet been made to study the composition of the precipitate obtained by the interaction of chromous chloride with potassium molybdocyanide. The course of this reaction has been investigated by means of conductometric and potentiometric titrations in aqueous medium and the results are incorporated in the present report.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents : Tetrapotassium octacyanomolybdate (IV) dihydrate, $K_4[Mo(CN)_8] \cdot 2H_2O$, was prepared by the method recommended by Fieser⁵. A weighed amount of the salt was dissolved in conductivity water and stored in a pyrex glass vessel wrapped in black paper. The strength of the solution was determined by titrating potentiometrically against potassium permanganate solution⁶. Chromous chloride crystals were prepared by the method recommended by Balthis and Bailar^{7,8}. These were dissolved in air-free conductivity water and the solution was stored and standardized according to the method used by Lingane and Pecsok⁹.

Titrations : The conductometric titrations were performed with the help of Cambridge conductivity bridge (No. L-350140) with a dip cell (No. PR 9510, cell constant = 1.46). A Pye Precision Vernier Potentiometer (Cat. No. 7568) in conjunction with a ballistic galvanometer and lamp and scale arrangement was used for potential measurements. A platinum wire (1 cm.) fused in Pyrex glass tube was used as indicator electrode and S.C.E. as the reference. The two halves of the cell were connected by KCl-agar bridge.

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The direct titrations were performed taking chromous chloride in the cell and potassium octacyanomolybdate (IV) in the burette and *vice versa* for the reverse titrations. After each addition of the titrant, solutions were stirred by a current of purified nitrogen gas which ensured a through mixing and maintained an inert atmosphere to check the oxidation of chromous chloride, especially while carrying out the direct titrations.

10.0 ml. of the titre solution was taken in the cell each time and the end-point was located graphically. The titrations were performed at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The titration curves (Fig. 1, curves I and II) illustrate the changes occurring in the conductance of solution when $K_4[Mo(CN)_8]$ is added to $CrCl_2$ and *vice versa*. In both the direct and reverse titrations, a break in titration curves was observed at the stoichiometric end-point where the molecular ratio of $Cr^{2+} : [Mo(CN)_8]^{4-}$ ions is 1 : 1, corresponding to the formation and precipitation of $K_2Cr^{II}[Mo^{IV}(CN)_8]$.

Fig. 1: Electrometric Titration Curves.

(I) & (III) 10ml. M/75 $CrCl_2$ with M/20 $K_4 Mo(CN)_8$,

(II) 10ml. M/75 $K_4 Mo(CN)_8$ with M/10 $CrCl_2$

Potentiometric titrations carried out with $CrCl_2$ in the cell give typical curves (Fig. 1, curve III) and here too, a ratio of 1 : 1 between the reactants was found to exist. Titrations carried out in the reverse manner were not successful. In each case, the molar ratio has been found to be independent of concentration of the reactants. The probable reaction for this ratio may, therefore, be given as :

The compound, $K_2Cr[Mo(CN)_8]$, in all probability, is not a complex compound of Cr(II), in the sense that Cr is not in the coordination zone; it is a compound of the type of $NaZn[UO_2(CH_3COO)_3]$. The potential and conductivity changes, as shown in the electrometric titration curves are due to the insoluble nature of the compound, which precipitates during titration.

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